

Futures of Business Education

ABIS KNOWLEDGE INTO ACTION FORUM, MAY 10-11 2022

On May 10-11, 2022 [ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society](#) convened its 8th [Knowledge Into Action Forum](#) during which speakers and participants engaged in keynote speeches, panel discussions and interactive sessions on the timely topic of "Futures of Business Education". The event took place online on May 10 and in person in Brussels on May 11.

True to its mission, ABIS believes that more than ever **business schools need to take responsibility for the mindsets, frameworks and management theories they teach** and to **transform their practices, curricula and research** as laid out into our recent [position paper](#).

Building on the growing foresight knowledge and competences ABIS have been developing, we approached this topic through the lens of **futures studies, foresight and anticipatory governance**. The aim was to offer original, novel insights and solutions to foster **pedagogical innovation, interdisciplinary and epistemic dialogue around management theory** as well as **institutional transformation** in business education.

Audience

The Forum welcomed business schools' Rectors and Vice-Rectors, deans, management involved in learning and teaching, faculty members, researchers, students as well as employers. We were pleased to:

- have over **70 registrations**
- from which we welcomed **50 participants** at the online and offline event
- representing **35 organizations...** and **18 countries!**

If you missed the event, you can now find **session summaries, available recordings, presentations** and **resources for further learning** in the following pages.

Opening remarks and keynote speech: "Futures studies - what is in it for business education?"

After a welcome speech by Karolina Sobczak, Knowledge Manager at ABIS, and opening remarks by **Baback Yazdani**, Chair of the Board of Directors, ABIS and Executive Dean, Nottingham Business School, **Njeri Mwagiru**, Senior Futurist, Institute for Futures Research, Stellenbosch Business School gave an insightful opening speech. Her remarks addressed the relevance of future studies approaches and frameworks to business schools and businesses in society. After highlighting the main changes that business education has undergone since it was formalized, the speaker zoomed into today's main critique: **current curricula have been perpetuating problematic paradigms** from the industrialization era. There is a disjunction

between what business education claims to be advancing and what are the actual outcomes, with business bearing responsibility for many crises we have to grapple with. At the same time, business is a key engine and driver of innovation and needs specific skills and capabilities. Given this tension, it is important to **identify the new trajectory for business, business schools and society in the 21st century**. Future studies offer a lens to understand the evolution of the field, explore the emerging trends as well as anticipate and prepare for multiples possibilities / scenarios for change. Several framework and approaches were mentioned, such as the foresight framework by Voros, the futures triangle by Inayatullah and the [Scenario Exploration System](#), which ABIS has been championing. These are helpful tools to **understand what is happening and why** - what are the patterns of change in business education and in society? where the points of intersection, disruption and discontinuity? what shall we do with these insights going forward? -, to **reconsider assumptions, concepts and narratives about business education** in a context where society is pushing toward sustainability and lastly to **envision and shape desired futures**. This last point underlines the **role of agency and responsible leadership**: future studies approaches not only help to prepare for the future, but also to shape it in the way we prefer, pushing us to address risks and maximise opportunities for more responsible business education.

What kind of business is business education promoting?

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Panel discussion: "Transforming business education for sustainable futures"

- **Cédric Bachellerie** – Managing Director, Sustainamics
- **Natalia Olyneć** - Head of Sustainability, IMD
- **Peter Wells** – Chief Higher Education, UNESCO
- Moderator: **Karolina Sobczak** – Knowledge Manager, ABIS

The panel focused emerging pathways from multiple perspectives to uplevel the role of business schools to ensure sustainable futures. The moderator set forth key undertakings by the European Commission on the changes in education needed to support the EU goals within the [EU Green Deal](#), such as the [European Skills Agenda](#) and the most recent [Learning for environmental sustainability proposal](#). 2022 has also been declared the [European Year of](#)

[Youth](#) to recognize youth's raising concerns on societal issues, and promote their engagement to build a better, greener and more inclusive future.

Peter Wells acknowledged the need for change in the education sector in light of the critical challenges over the next decade. UNESCO has recently published the "[Knowledge-driven actions: Transforming higher education for global sustainability](#)" report by the Independent Expert Group on Universities and the 2030 Agenda. The experts reported that **we need new institutions, new types of learning, and to face new types of learners**. There is a need for a radical change for higher education institutions to provide lifelong learning, and to review their relationships with local communities, strengthening ties, focusing on their needs and providing new opportunities.

Natalie Olyne explained how IMD influences organizations to integrate sustainability by focusing on responsible leadership development, cutting-edge education, equity, inclusion and diversity, as well mobility and emissions. These dimensions are important to **engage stakeholders**, especially students, alumni, and business leaders, and to ensure an impact on business. Notably IMD also launched the [Business Schools for Climate Leadership](#), a collaboration of eight leading European business schools, joining forces to help business leaders combat the climate crisis and accelerate their actions to meet the goals of the Paris agreement. Due to further engagement, new business schools are developing similar initiatives in other geographies.

Cedric Bachellerie addressed the issue of core competences for sustainability, who needs to be upskilled and when we need this to happen – which is now! It is important to **reskill the current workforce, in particular leaders** (CEOs, senior managers and board members) as they are expected to deliver not just profit, but many more non-financial impacts than before, while avoiding dangers of greenwashing. Senior leaders spend little time in personal development, however there is a talent gap there and they need to be supported to invest time in learning and acquiring new knowledge.

Environmental literacy should be a key competence transferred to business school students, as they will likely hold these leading positions in business and beyond. A lively Q&A discussion followed.

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The two following sessions zoomed into a specific theme which is going to have a great impact on the future of business education, and its ability to address pressing societal challenges: pedagogy and skills development.

Pedagogy and skills development focus

Interactive session I: "Applying the European competence framework on sustainability"

- **Ulrike Pisiotis** - Policy Officer, DG Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, European Commission

Dr Pisiotis introduced the [GreenComp](#), a new framework for sustainability competences. Greencomp stems from a context in which the European Commission put sustainability at the core of its policies and it aligns with key policies as the EU Green Deal, or the EU Skills Agenda. Most of EU citizens are concerned about protecting the environment and the need to address climate change. There is a need for education and training to prepare people to address these challenges. The objective of GreenComp is to set out these skills and to support the adoption of sustainable and responsible behaviour. GreenComp aims to **promote sustainability values** (fairness, make people understand that they are part of nature, respect of the environment) as well as **systems thinking**

and futures literacy to help people reimagine and develop alternative scenarios to lead to a new reality. Finally, the GreenComp seeks to unleash action for sustainability to lead to a change of paradigm of action and a new relation with the environment by **developing new competences, knowledge, skills, and attitudes**. With these new skills and attitudes, we expect learners to be able to think and develop new sustainable practices. In breakout rooms, participants discussed how to apply the framework and develop such competences in their schools. Some participants pointed out similarities with pre-existing tools, while highlighting the benefits of such a recognized, overarching conceptual framework and the opportunity to target and reskill new demographics and engage more people.

Interactive session II: "Taking climate leadership: preparing students for challenging times"

- **Petra Molthan-Hill** - Professor of Sustainable Management and Education for Sustainable Development, Nottingham Business School, NTU

Petra Molthan-Hill focused on how to prepare students for a climate change context and to educate them to address this issue. There is a significant gap between the number of Business Schools that believe that they should teach about climate change and the number of Business Schools that actually include it in the curriculum. Often climate change is taught from the perspective of **climate science, but it is important to learn about solutions** (what to do and

how to solve climate change), for instance what are the best solutions to reduce GHG emissions? Professors, students and the broader public do need to understand not only the broader concept, but also what are the solutions needed to address it. Also, it is important to learn about climate adaptation and to **balance adaptation and mitigation** without sacrificing one for the other. [The Carbon literacy project](#) offers a way to do that by teaching about the problem of climate change, the possible solutions, and adopting an **interactive approach** with a focus on solutions which are not only related to CO₂ emissions, but on all greenhouse gasses. In the breakout rooms, participants discussed how to integrate carbon literacy within their curricula or teaching. Some teachers shared their experiences, while other participants mentioned how they are take action as a result of this training, such as reducing the carbon footprint of research centres and practicing what they preach to show coherence.

The image shows a presentation slide on the left and a video call window on the right. The slide has a pink header and footer. The main text on the slide is in black and pink. The video call window shows a woman with glasses and a black top, identified as Petra Molthan-Hill.

Halve CO₂ emissions by around 2030

In order to limit global warming to 1.5° C, the IPCC stresses that the world needs **to halve CO₂ emissions by around 2030** and reach Net Zero CO₂ emissions by mid-century.

In addition, the IPCC emphasises ***the need for deep reductions in non-CO₂ emissions across the economy*** to achieve this limit.

CDP (2020) *Foundations for science-based net-zero target setting in the corporate sector:*
<https://sciencebasedtargets.org/resources/files/foundations-for-net-zero-full-paper.pdf> p5

NTU

Remove Spotlight
Petra Molthan-Hill

Fishbowl discussion: "Implications for institutional development"

This final session of Day 1 harvested the learnings from the morning and the interactive sessions and reflected on how they influence the future institutional developments of business schools. All participants engaged in a fishbowl discussion and addressed a variety of topics. One of the first questions addressed how business schools should be organised and what should business schools leaders (deans and administrators) prioritize. Echoing the panel discussion, in the future there should be **new operational practices and integration with local communities**. Working together and collaborate with

stakeholders is going to be very important and has a lot of potential, also within the wider university. In contexts where the idea of sustainability is less developed, students play a critical role in pushing for sustainability. However, business schools are going to grapple with their historical baggage. Incremental change within business schools is unlikely to lead to a fast shift in their output. A more **radical change is needed regarding priorities and expected outputs**. Part of the problem are the silo-like organization and cultural resistance to change. However, there is also potential within motivated academics that are willing to conduct cross-disciplinary research and establish connections with different faculties. Also, the current treatment of education and research as a market, with business schools needing to grow and attract more students to be financially sustainable, is a threat to the quality and aim of the work done by business schools. The session represented an opportunity to reflect and to think outside of day-to-day work to see how can we **re-educate students, but also to re-educate leaders** to build a sustainable future and to **reconsider the institutional nature of business schools**. A key final remark was that we need to learn how to **connect changes in business schools and changes in society**, because these are intertwined and identifying these connections will be critical to foster change.

Integrating sustainability within the practices of business schools, through alliances with stakeholders or by involving students can be an enabler of change.

Day 2 – May 11

During the second day participants engaged in an **active and dynamic exploration of futures of business education** via facilitated foresight tools and methods. The objective was to explore the driving forces and underlying factors that are going to shape how business education is going to look like in the decades to come. These insights are going to inform an **emerging initiative for the ABIS network aimed to accelerate the needed changes in business schools via the identification of desired scenarios.**

Interactive session I: "Scenario Building"

In the first session, participants reflected on what **key factors and patterns of events** will determine future outcomes in the business education environment in the next 30 years. The ABIS team presented the context and aims of the broader initiative on "[Building future scenarios of business education](#)" and the specific exercise, and then participants engaged in 1,5 hour brainstorming session. The outcomes of the session will be summarized by the ABIS team and further developed in an upcoming workshop on June 15.

Interactive session II: "Envisioning the future of business education"

In order to provide participants with a sense of completion, the final session of the event gave the opportunity to them to develop one storyline in which change in business education can happen. Several ideas regarding:

- evidence suggesting that the current business education system is under strain
- a vision of the emerging future
- examples of elements of the future business education already exist
- innovations that are responding to the pressures for change and might be growth points of the future business education

To summarize, participants highlighted key **current disconnects of business education from reality** such as irresponsiveness to societal needs, outdated assessment models, no focus on skills development, elitist and siloed approach, and reached a new vision for business education characterized by the **transmission of transversal skills**, a **culture of stewardship** and **business as a commons**, **hybrid, challenge-based life-long learning**, **inclusion** of many different talents as well as forms of **accountability**. More details on the findings can be accessed [HERE](#).

PATTERN

For a better resolution, please click on the link at the end of the previous paragraph.

Resources for further use

In order to keep up with the objectives of the event, in this section we are sharing some useful resources and materials that our participants, members and any interested stakeholders are encouraged to access and use in their business, research and teaching practices:

- [Keynote speech Njeri Mwagiru presentation](#)
- ["Applying the European competence framework on sustainability" - Ulrike Pisiotis presentation](#)
- ["Taking climate leadership: preparing students for challenging times" - Petra Molthan-Hill presentation](#)
- [ABIS Position paper "Transforming business education for sustainability: the case for paradigm shifts in pedagogy and theory"](#)
- [ABIS Special Issue: Best Sustainability Teaching Practices 2022](#), published in the Emerald Journal of International Education in Business
- [Scenario Exploration System](#)
- Research paper: [Three Horizons: A pathways practice for transformation](#), [Bill Sharpe et al.](#)

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank our **Laurent Bontoux** - Senior Foresight for Policy Expert, Joint Research Centre, European Commission for his useful insights and guidance in steering the goals of the event and live workshops in the right direction.

Lastly, the event could not have happened without our excellent speakers and all the participants! Thank you!

Feedback

We at ABIS are thrilled that our participants and speakers enjoyed this year's theme and discussions. Here is what they shared with us!

"Very relevant as this is a hot topic, now and well into the future"

"Thank you for today, it was amazing. It is so exciting to see one's ideas put to use to shape the future"

"Both you and your colleagues impressed me massively today with your unwavering professionalism"

"I trust ABIS who are always good at being ahead of the curve. Congratulations on a super position paper! "

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See you soon at our future events!

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